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DETECTOR PERFORMANCE BY USING PHYSICS PROCESSES

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Abstract:

This deliverable presents an assessment of the detector capabilities at a 10 TeV muon collider. Select physics processes targeting Higgs bosons, W bosons, or dark matter production are used to illustrate the detector performance. Results from detailed detector simulations demonstrate that excellent physics performance can be achieved despite the challenging beam-induced background environment.

MuCol Consortium, 2026

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This document summarizes the detector performance in a selected number of physics benchmark channels for a 10 TeV centre-of-mass muon collider, as prepared within the International Muon Collider Collaboration under the Horizon Europe MuCol project (WP2 — Physics and Detector Requirements).

The report includes studies based on the latest simulation and reconstruction software and the state-of-the-art detector concepts, MUSIC and MAIA, which were submitted to the 2025 European Strategy process.

The selected physics benchmark processes are introduced, together with a brief explanation of the relevant event reconstruction performances as evaluated by the two detector concepts. The physics benchmarks are then used to evaluate the suitability of the detector concepts in the 10 TeV data-taking, and the corresponding physics potential is quantified in terms of achievable precision on key observables or sensitivity curves as a function of model parameters.

These results cover an example of the breadth of the physics programme of a 10 TeV muon collider, while probing several aspects of the reconstruction performance of the studied detector concepts. This document will serve as a reference for future physics performance studies exploiting the full detector simulation in the MuCol framework.

1. INTRODUCTION

Muon Colliders have the potential to reach multi-TeV center-of-mass energies and high luminosity, combining the reach of a hadron collider, with the precision of an e^+e^- machine. Muon collisions provide a unique opportunity to measure particle physics phenomena at high energies, given the well-defined initial states, the low levels of physics backgrounds, and the large production cross sections.

The current proposal of the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) aims at 10 TeV center-of-mass energy collisions, with a possible initial phase at 3 TeV. However, the presence of beam-induced background (BIB) resulting from the decay of beam muons poses unique challenges for detector development and event reconstruction.

This deliverable presents an assessment of detector performance using benchmark physics processes. The document collects studies performed using a detailed detector simulation to demonstrate the feasibility of a broad physics programme with state-of-the-art detector designs despite the challenging background environment.

2. SIMULATION AND RECONSTRUCTION SOFTWARE

The simulation of detector response, digitisation of the energy depositions and reconstruction of the collisions events was performed with the MuonColliderSoft software stack [1, 2] within the Key4hep software ecosystem [3, 4]. Compact dd4hep detector models for simulation with the GEANT4 program are available on GitHub [5]. The simulation framework includes detailed modelling of the detector geometry, material properties, and the response of active detector elements.

The Monte Carlo samples for signal processes and associated physics backgrounds are produced with the WHIZARD [6] and MadGraph5 aMC@NLO [7] event generators, interfaced where necessary with PYTHIA for particle hadronization and showering [8]. Minimal requirements are applied at the generation level to ensure unbiased measurements.

The signal and physics background samples are processed with the simulation and reconstruction tools of the muon collider software framework. The simulated energy depositions produced by the machine-induced backgrounds are obtained from the FLUKA particle transport code [9, 10] and superimposed on each physics process event-by-event before reconstruction. Reconstruction and large parts of the analysis chain are run using the Gaudi-based event processing framework of Key4hep. The k4MarlinWrapper is used to run many existing components from previous studies developed inside the iLCSoft framework [11] using Marlin [12] and LCIO. This notably includes the PandoraPFA algorithm for particle flow reconstruction.

3. DETECTOR MODELS

Two detector configurations optimised for 10 TeV data-taking are considered for the physics performance studies: the *MUSIC* and *MAIA* detector concepts, which are briefly summarised below.

3.1. MUSIC

The *MUSIC* (MUon System for Interesting Collisions) detector concept [13], designed for 10 TeV collisions, has a length of 11.4 m and a diameter of 12.8 m. It features an all-silicon tracking system followed by a calorimetric system and a muon detection system, with a 5 T superconducting solenoid placed between the electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters.

The tracking system consists of a vertex detector with five cylindrical barrel layers ($25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ pixels, 5 μm spatial resolution, 30 ps timing resolution), and an inner and outer tracker, each comprising three barrel layers (50 $\mu\text{m} \times 1$ mm macropixels, 7 $\mu\text{m} \times 90 \mu\text{m}$ spatial resolution, 60 ps timing resolution). The electromagnetic calorimeter is a semi-homogeneous crystal calorimeter (CRILIN) with lead-fluoride crystals providing 26.5 radiation lengths and excellent energy resolution. The hadronic calorimeter is an iron-scintillator sampling calorimeter with 70 layers totalling seven nuclear interaction lengths.

3.2. MAIA

The *MAIA* (Muon Accelerator Instrumented Apparatus) detector concept [14] is designed for maximum hermiticity given the constraints of shielding nozzles. It has an overall length of 12 m and diameter of 14 m, featuring an all-silicon tracking system, a silicon-tungsten electromagnetic sampling calorimeter, an iron-scintillator hadronic sampling calorimeter, and an RPC-based muon detection system.

A key distinguishing feature of *MAIA* is the placement of a thin superconducting solenoid between the tracking system and the electromagnetic calorimeter, which adds approximately $4 X_0$ and reduces the incoming BIB particle flux by a factor of 10. The vertex detector consists of four barrel layers with double-layer endcap disks, and the inner tracker has six barrel layers and eleven endcap disks. The electromagnetic calorimeter uses silicon-tungsten technology similar to the CMS high-granularity calorimeter for the HL-LHC upgrade.

4. BENCHMARK PHYSICS PROCESSES

A set of three physics benchmarks was selected to investigate the expected performance of the detector concepts being designed or refined within the MuCol project with the aid of full detector simulation. These processes were selected to give a representative coverage of the physics potential of the machine and be sensitive to a wide range of particle and event reconstruction methods, while using a limited amount of computational resources. All studied benchmarks are reported under the assumption of exploiting data from a single experiment.

4.1. HIGGS AND DI-HIGGS BOSON PRODUCTION

The study of the Higgs boson plays a central role in modern particle physics. The Higgs boson is at the heart of the electroweak symmetry breaking and the muon collider will enable a variety of tests of the most basic properties of the unified electroweak-Higgs sector. At multi-TeV muon collisions, Higgs bosons are mainly produced via vector-boson-fusion (VBF) processes, characterized by large cross sections (shown in Figure 1) that enable high-statistics measurements. The large Higgs sample and low physics backgrounds enable precision tests of Higgs couplings as well as direct measurements of the Higgs self-coupling.

Figure 1: Cross sections for various Higgs boson production processes in $\mu^+\mu^-$ collisions as a function of the center-of-mass energy. Initial-state radiation is not included in cross-section calculation. Taken from Ref. [15].

The large expected sample of Higgs bosons is used to extract measurements of the Higgs boson couplings to the other Standard Model fermions and bosons, as well as its self-coupling.

4.2. W BOSON PRODUCTION

Muon colliders can possibly enable a precision physics programme targeting the determination of electroweak particle masses and couplings. The precise determination of the W boson mass could be one of the key goals of this precision electroweak programme. The W boson mass is a fundamental parameter of the Standard Model whose value, together with the top quark and Higgs boson masses, constrains the internal consistency of the electroweak sector and can reveal signs of new physics

through quantum corrections. Tensions between recent measurements at hadron colliders have highlighted the importance of independent, high-precision determinations of m_W using complementary experimental techniques.

At multi-TeV muon collisions, W bosons are copiously produced via vector boson fusion and scattering processes, with cross sections of several picobarns at $\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV. The hadronic decay channel $W \rightarrow qq'$ provides direct access to the W mass through the dijet invariant mass distribution, exploiting the large statistics and the clean initial state of the muon collider. This approach is complementary to the leptonic measurements traditionally performed at hadron colliders.

4.3. THERMAL DARK MATTER

Muon colliders offer unique sensitivity to dark matter candidates. Among the various possibilities, Weakly Interacting Massive Particles (WIMP) are among the best-motivated models. Higgsino- and wino-like states, the supersymmetric partners of the Higgs and W fields respectively, are a notable model-specific example of a WIMP. These particles could be produced in pairs via Drell-Yan and vector boson fusion processes. The small mass splitting between the charged and neutral components of the electroweak multiplet, approximately 160 MeV for the wino and 350 MeV for the higgsino, results in a macroscopic lifetime for the charged state, which decays to the neutral state and a soft pion. This produces a characteristic "disappearing track" signature: a short track in the inner detector with no associated hits in the outer layers.

Figure 2 shows the expected production cross-section for these processes, highlighting how these particles could be within experimental reach even with limited integrated luminosities.

Figure 2: Production cross sections for pairs of the charged component of the electroweak multiplet at $\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV. Shown are the cases of pure wino (green) and pure higgsino (orange). The full (dashed) lines correspond to Drell-Yan (VBF) production. Taken from Ref. [16].

5. EXPECTED DETECTOR PERFORMANCE

Despite the different choices made in the detailed designs of the two detector concepts under evaluation, the particle-level performance was found to be comparable. Since future changes in the design of the detector concepts is likely to yield larger effects than the observed differences at the time of writing, the following section provides a summary of the observed performances without making distinctions.

5.1. TRACK RECONSTRUCTION

Track reconstruction in the muon collider environment is challenging due to the high density of BIB hits [17]. Two algorithms were employed: conformal tracking and a combinatorial Kalman filter approach implemented in the ACTS tracking library. The main differences in these algorithms relate to the processing time (with the combinatorial Kalman filter approach being substantially faster) and number of “fake” track candidates, i.e. unmatched to a real particle, which are found in each detector region. Both implementations achieve a track reconstruction efficiency of about 75% at $\theta = 13^\circ$ and close to 100% at $\theta = 89^\circ$. This also applies for the special short tracks used in the searches for dark matter. The transverse momentum resolution ranges from $\delta p_T/p_T^2 \approx 10^{-3} \text{ GeV}^{-1}$ for low-momentum tracks at forward angles to $\delta p_T/p_T^2 \approx 10^{-5} \text{ GeV}^{-1}$ for TeV tracks at central angles.

5.2. FLAVOUR TAGGING

The identification of jet flavours is performed using relatively simple algorithms that rely on the reconstruction of secondary vertices within jets. The tagging algorithm achieves an efficiency of about 45% for b-jets with p_T around 20 GeV, increasing to about 70% for p_T around 140 GeV, with a c-jet misidentification rate of about 20% and light-quark jet fake rate from 0.1% to 5%. Future implementations relying on modern machine learning-based methods such as those used at the LHC experiments are expected to significantly improve these performances.

5.3. CALORIMETRY AND PARTICLE FLOW

High-level reconstructed particle objects are found using the PandoraPFA algorithm with tracks and calorimeter hits as inputs. The energy depositions in the calorimeter systems above thresholds defined to reduce BIB contamination are clustered using recursive algorithms that are first seeded by the presence of charged tracks reaching the inner calorimeter surface, and later by highly energetic localised energy depositions. The reconstructed clusters are then matched with charged tracks and their combined properties are used to form combined particle flow objects (PFO), which are then identified as electrons, photons, as well as charged and neutral hadrons.

Photons were found to have a reconstruction efficiency of about 78% for energies below 50 GeV and 98% above 300 GeV, with an energy resolution of 13% at low energies and 1.5% above 400 GeV. The largest source of inefficiency comes from the misidentification of photons as electrons or pions due to BIB contamination. Optimised algorithms are expected to recover these inefficiencies down to very low energies but were not employed in these studies.

Hadronic jets are reconstructed using the k_t or anti- k_t jet algorithms on the reconstructed PFOs and are then required to satisfy additional cleaning cuts, such as having at least one associated charged

track, to reject BIB contributions. The jet selection efficiency is 85% for p_T around 20 GeV and 90% for p_T around 200 GeV. The jet p_T resolution is 35% at 20 GeV and 20% at 200 GeV.

5.4. MUON RECONSTRUCTION AND IDENTIFICATION

Neither of the two detector concepts foresees a magnetic field in the region dedicated to the muon system. For this reason, the muon system contributes exclusively to the particle identification by building stubs which are then matched to tracks in the tracking detector, which provides the momentum measurement. The identification efficiency is of about 20% in the forward angular regions ($10^\circ < \theta < 20^\circ$) due to BIB contamination, while it is close to 100% for $40^\circ < \theta < 140^\circ$.

6. SUMMARY OF PHYSICS STUDIES

6.1. HIGGS AND DI-HIGGS BOSON MEASUREMENTS

H \rightarrow bb cross section: The measurement of the H \rightarrow bb cross section is performed in the dijet final state [15]. The two highest p_T jets in the event are selected and required to be identified as b-jets. To remove the low-momentum background, a transverse momentum of $p_T > 40$ GeV for both jets is required.

The generation cross sections, the selection efficiencies, the jet identification efficiencies, and the expected number of observed signal and background events are reported in Table 1.

Process	σ [fb]	$\epsilon_{preselect}$ [%]	ϵ_{tag} [%]	N_{exp}
$\mu^+ \mu^- \rightarrow H(\rightarrow b\bar{b})X$	490	22.2	32.4	351518
$\mu^+ \mu^- \rightarrow H(\rightarrow c\bar{c})X$	24.3	22.2	4.49	2422
$\mu^+ \mu^- \rightarrow q\bar{q}\nu_\ell\bar{\nu}_\ell$	2674	25.6	5.00	341598
$\mu^+ \mu^- \rightarrow q\bar{q}\ell\ell$	4339	1.86	1.31	10533
$\mu^+ \mu^- \rightarrow q\bar{q}\ell\nu_\ell$	9763	21.46	0.10	20974

Table 1: Generation cross section, preselection efficiency, b-tagging efficiency, and expected events for the signal and physics background processes in the H \rightarrow bb analysis for $\mu^+\mu^-$ collisions at 10 TeV and $L = 10 \text{ ab}^{-1}$. X indicates both $\nu\nu$ and $\ell\ell$. Taken from Ref. [15].

The main source of background is the $\mu^+\mu^- \rightarrow q\bar{q}\nu\nu$ process. In this process, most of the qq pairs are produced through a Z boson, which has a sizable branching fraction to b quarks and can mimic the signal. A fit to the dijet invariant mass distribution is performed to extract the signal yield using an unbinned maximum likelihood, with the H \rightarrow bb and qq $\nu\nu$ yields as free parameters. Other background yields are fixed to the expectation from simulation.

At 10 TeV, with 10 ab^{-1} of data, a statistical uncertainty on the production cross section of 0.28% is expected.

H \rightarrow WW* cross section: The measurement of the H \rightarrow WW* cross section is performed in the semileptonic decay mode, where one W boson decays into a muon and a muonic neutrino while the other decays hadronically into two jets, yielding the final state H \rightarrow WW* \rightarrow qq $\mu\nu$ [15]. H \rightarrow WW* candidates are defined by associating a high- p_T prompt muon with two reconstructed jets. Muons are required to satisfy $10 \text{ GeV} < p_T < 1000 \text{ GeV}$ and $10^\circ < \theta < 170^\circ$, where the upper p_T limit rejects fake tracks from beam-induced backgrounds. If multiple identified muons pass the selection, the most

isolated one is retained. Before selecting the candidate jets, a fake-jet cleaning criterion is applied, requiring at least one track in the jet with $p_T > 2$ GeV, along with jet p_T and angular corrections. Jets are selected if they satisfy $20 \text{ GeV} < p_T < 2000 \text{ GeV}$ and $10^\circ < \theta < 170^\circ$, and the jet pair with invariant mass closest to the nominal W boson mass is retained.

Figure 3: Stacked distributions of the BDT scores to separate the $H \rightarrow WW^*$ signal from the backgrounds with a Higgs boson (left) and the non-resonant backgrounds (right). Taken from Ref. [15].

After the preselection, two Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) classifiers, shown in Figure 3, are trained to distinguish the signal from backgrounds containing a Higgs boson (HX) and from non-resonant backgrounds (qqX), respectively. The BDTs exploit properties of the reconstructed muon (p_T , θ , isolation, ΔR to the jets), the two jets (p_T , θ , component numbers), the hadronic W candidate (p_T , θ , invariant mass), the Higgs boson candidate (θ , invariant mass, acollinearity angles), and global event observables (missing transverse energy and scalar sum of transverse momenta). The statistical sensitivity is evaluated fitting the two-dimensional distribution of the BDT outputs within a maximum-likelihood fit. Despite the highly unfavourable signal-to-background ratio in the selected sample, the BDT classifiers achieve sufficient separation in the 2D score space.

Assuming negligible uncertainties on the selection efficiency and integrated luminosity, the resulting statistical uncertainty on the $H \rightarrow WW^*$ production cross section is 0.58% at 10 TeV with 10 ab^{-1} .

HH cross section and trilinear self-coupling extraction: At least four jets with $p_T > 20$ GeV are required in the event, and at least two must be identified as b-jets [15]. To reconstruct the HH events, all possible two-jet combinations are formed, with at least one jet in each pair required to be b-tagged. The two Higgs boson candidates are built from the jet pairs whose invariant masses m_{12} and m_{34} minimise the figure of merit $F = \sqrt{((m_{12} - m_H)^2 + (m_{34} - m_H)^2)}$. The main physics background arises from processes with four heavy-quark jets in the final state, $\mu^+\mu^- \rightarrow q_h q_h q_h q_h X$ ($q_h = b$ or c), which involve multiple intermediate electroweak gauge bosons. An important additional background is the single-Higgs process $\mu^+\mu^- \rightarrow H(\rightarrow bb) q_h q_h X$, where the HHH vertex is not present.

A Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is trained using nine kinematic observables to separate signal from backgrounds: the invariant masses of the leading and sub-leading Higgs candidates, the maximum separation angle between the two candidates, angular variables of the highest- p_T jets relative to each candidate and the z-axis, and the four jet transverse momenta. Good separation between HH signal and background processes is achieved. The HH signal yield is extracted by fitting the MLP output distribution using pseudo-experiments, following the same procedure as for $H \rightarrow bb$ and $H \rightarrow WW^*$.

At 10 TeV with 10 ab^{-1} , about 2100 signal events are expected, and a statistical uncertainty of 6% on the double-Higgs production cross section is obtained.

A measurement of the trilinear self-coupling λ_3 can then be performed and requires distinguishing double-Higgs events originating from the diagram involving an intermediate off-shell H^* from all other HH production contributions, exploiting the distinct kinematics of HH pairs produced via the trilinear vertex.

To separate the signal from backgrounds and to distinguish HH events sensitive to λ_3 from other HH contributions, two MLPs are trained independently. The first MLP is the same used in the HH cross-section analysis to separate SM HH signal from physics backgrounds. The second MLP is trained on four kinematic variables (i.e. the angle between the two Higgs boson momenta, the angles of the highest- p_T jets with respect to the z-axis, and the helicity angle of the Higgs candidates) to separate HH production via an off-shell H^* from other HH diagrams. For each $\kappa_{\lambda_3} = \lambda_3/\lambda_3^{\text{SM}}$ hypothesis, two-dimensional templates are built using the outputs of both MLPs, normalised to the expected signal and background yields.

Figure 4: ΔLL as a function of the κ_{λ_3} hypothesis. Taken from Ref. [15].

A profile likelihood scan, shown in Figure 4, is performed to extract a confidence interval for the trilinear Higgs self-coupling, which is found to be $0.94 < \kappa_{\lambda_3} < 1.08$ at 68% C.L. for 10 TeV with 10 ab^{-1} .

6.2. W BOSON MEASUREMENTS

W Boson Mass from Hadronic Decays: The abundant production of W bosons via vector boson fusion at a 10 TeV muon collider enables a precision determination of the W boson mass using the hadronic decay channel $W \rightarrow qq'$. The measurement exploits the large statistics of the $\mu^+\mu^- \rightarrow qqX$ process, where the dijet invariant mass distribution of on-shell W bosons provides direct sensitivity to m_W . This approach is complementary to traditional template-fit methods used at hadron colliders, which rely on leptonic W decays.

The analysis selects events containing two jets consistent with the hadronic decay of a W boson. Jets are reconstructed using the particle flow algorithm and are required to satisfy cleaning criteria to suppress BIB contamination, including the requirement of at least one associated charged track, and have a p_T larger than 20 GeV. Jet energy scale and resolution corrections, calibrated using the well-known $Z \rightarrow qq$ resonance available in the same dataset, are applied to improve the accuracy of the dijet invariant mass, shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Distribution of the expected di-jet invariant mass in 10 ab^{-1} of $\sqrt{s} = 10 \text{ TeV } \mu^+ \mu^-$ collisions, as recorded by the MAIA detector. The colored histograms represent the contributions of the main processes expected to contribute to this final state. Taken from Ref. [18].

The W boson mass is extracted from a template fit to the dijet invariant mass distribution. Templates are generated for different m_W hypotheses and compared to pseudo-data using a binned maximum likelihood. The dominant systematic uncertainties arise from the jet energy scale calibration and the modelling of the dijet mass resolution.

Preliminary studies [18] indicate that a statistical precision on m_W of down to 4 MeV is achievable with 10 ab^{-1} of data at 10 TeV. This would represent a significant improvement over current direct measurements from hadron collider experiments and demonstrates the potential of the muon collider environment for precision electroweak physics. Further studies are ongoing to fully characterise the systematic uncertainties and to extend the measurement to include leptonic W decay channels.

6.3. SEARCH FOR DARK MATTER

Disappearing Tracks from Wino and Higgsino Dark Matter: The search for disappearing tracks at the muon collider is particularly challenging due to the beam-induced background, which can produce hit combinations in the tracking detector that mimic the signal signature [16]. A dedicated strategy is employed to suppress BIB-induced fake tracks, exploiting timing information and spatial correlations of hits in the tracking layers. The selection requires reconstructed short tracks, built from hits in the inner detector layers using the CT algorithm, satisfying quality criteria on the number of hits, the track χ^2 , and timing consistency. After this selection, the average number of fake tracks from

BIB is reduced to below 0.1 per event. The studies of Ref. [16] were repeated using the MAIA detector concept and a combinatorial Kalman filter-based short track reconstruction finding results consistent with the previous studies.

The signal yields depend on the mass and lifetime of the chargino, as well as on the detector geometry. For the chargino masses probed at $\sqrt{s} = 10$ TeV, the signal acceptance times efficiency ranges from a few percent for higgsino-like states with short lifetimes to over 10% for wino-like states with longer lifetimes. A cut-and-count analysis is performed, requiring at least one disappearing track and applying kinematic selections on the track transverse momentum and polar angle to further reduce the residual background.

The results, shown in Figure 6, demonstrate that a 10 TeV muon collider with 10 ab^{-1} of data can probe thermal wino dark matter (with a mass of approximately 2.7 TeV) and thermal higgsino dark matter (with a mass of approximately 1.1 TeV), covering masses close to $\sqrt{s}/2$ in the lifetime range of 0.1–10 ns.

Figure 6: Expected sensitivity using 1 ab^{-1} of $10 \text{ TeV } \mu^+\mu^-$ collision data as a function of the χ^{\pm} mass and lifetime. Taken from Ref. [16].

Future improvements in track reconstruction algorithms and detector optimisation are expected to further enhance the sensitivity, particularly for the challenging short-lifetime higgsino scenario.

7. CONCLUSION

This deliverable demonstrates that state-of-the-art detector technologies and reconstruction algorithms enable a wide range of physics studies, from high-precision measurements of Higgs and W boson properties to the search for new particles and phenomena, at a 10 TeV muon collider.

The results obtained with detailed detector simulations, including the effects of beam-induced background, are consistent with target performance estimates, underscoring the capability of the detector configurations to effectively manage the challenging background environment.

Key findings include:

- Statistical uncertainties on Higgs cross sections of 0.28% ($H \rightarrow bb$) and 0.58% ($H \rightarrow WW^*$) at 10 TeV with 10 ab^{-1}

- Double Higgs production cross section measurable with 6% precision and $0.94 < \kappa_{\lambda_3} < 1.08$ at 68% C.L.
- W boson mass measurements with a precision down to about 4 MeV
- A potential to discover well motivated thermal dark matter candidates

Future efforts will focus on refining detector performance, incorporating additional physics channels, and further improving reconstruction algorithms. The detector requirements derived from these studies will guide the technical design of muon collider experiments and establish benchmarks for detector R&D priorities.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
BIB	Beam-Induced Background
BDT	Boosted Decision Tree
ECAL	Electromagnetic Calorimeter
HCAL	Hadronic Calorimeter
IMCC	International Muon Collider Collaboration
MAIA	Muon Accelerator Instrumented Apparatus
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MuC	Muon Collider
MUSIC	MUon System for Interesting Collisions
RPC	Resistive Plate Chamber
SM	Standard Model
SV	Secondary Vertex
VBF	Vector Boson Fusion